

SERVICE MARKETING STRATEGIES AND CUSTOMER SATISFACTION: EVIDENCE FROM COMMERCIAL BANKS IN SOUTHEAST, NIGERIA

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Abstract: This study examined the effect of service marketing strategies on customer satisfaction in Southeast, Nigeria. The research used Yamane's formula for a finite population to determine a sample of 400 respondents from 25,797,612 adult bank customers. Average Variance Extracted and Cronbach's Alpha were used to test the validity and reliability of a structured questionnaire. The research data were analyzed with standard multiple regression. The study determined a positive statistical influence of service process and communication on customer satisfaction. On the contrary, service features, service charges, service encounters, service participation, and service evidence had no statistical influence on customer satisfaction. The result implied that a unit increase in the flexibility of bank services and an increase in bank-customer contact increased the level of customer satisfaction. The research also suggested that for every unit increase in service options; service channels; customer involvement; service facilities; and a reduction in service charge, there was no increase in satisfaction of Southeast Bank customers. Therefore, the research recommended that banks should develop a customer-friendly service system that can reduce service time and increase service turnover. Bank managers were also advised to intensify efforts to provide financial information that enables customers to make informed decisions.

Keywords: Service marketing strategies, customer satisfaction, banks, Nigeria

1. Introduction

The crowd in customer care units of Nigerian commercial banks has increased recently. Banks are experiencing difficulty decongesting their hall as numerous customers troop in to resolve failed internet transactions, report payment card issues, and stop unauthorized deductions, to mention but a few. The bank premises are overstretched as unresolved banking issues continue to manifest. Scholars also reported cases of network failures, poor complaints handling, delayed services, and failed transactions (Osiegbe & Onuorah, 2018; Ikechi, Robinson & Emelike, 2018; Ebire and Onmonya, 2018; Ezu & Chris-Ejiogu, 2018). These raise questions about the effectiveness of banks' service marketing strategies. Service marketing strategies (SMSs) are methods adopted

by firms to provide a competitive customer experience. They are useful techniques that influence service demand, satisfy customers, and achieve a firm's objectives (Do & Vu, 2020; Thwala & Slabbert, 2018; Abidemi, Halim & Alshuaibi, 2017; Sohrabi, Khanbolooki & Ghazavi, 2017). Sometimes, banks assume that they adopt satisfactory SMSs without knowing when they fall short of customer expectations. New service knowledge, changes in customer taste, and bad service experience affect customer attitude and purchasing behavior without a sign. As a result, banks attempt to modify their SMSs to achieve customer satisfaction. Customer satisfaction is a feeling that service performance meets customer-perceived expectations (Bracíníková & Matušínková, 2017; Kursunluoglu, 2011; Zeithaml, Bitner & Gremler, 2009). Available literature has indicated some studies on SMSs and customer satisfaction in other parts of the world (Budiyono, Tho'in, Muliastari, & Putri, 2021; Khatab, Esmaeel & Othman, 2019; Kraa, Opoku-Mensah, Kwade & Boateng, 2018) except in Southeast, Nigeria. The geographic gap exposed a difference in customer requirements and banking operations thereby making the previous results non-generalizable and providing support for a study in Southeast, Nigeria. Therefore, the present survey examined the effect of SMSs on customer satisfaction in Southeast, Nigeria. The specific objectives were to establish the influence of service features; service process; service charges; service communication; service encounter; service participation; and service evidence on satisfaction of Southeast bank customers. This section is followed by a literature review, conceptual framework, research methodology, results, and discussion.

2. Literature Review

2.1 Service Marketing Strategies

2.1.1 Service Features: Service features involve the nature and type of banking operations, employee proficiency, and non-banking attributes. Lovelock & Wirtz, (2011) classified financial services into core services (savings, loans, Western Union) and supplementary services (information, consultations, order taking, billing, payment, hospitality, and customer service). Commercial banks maintain savings, current, and joint accounts, suggest viable investments, and provide internet-based services (Sintani, Mantikei, Anggariani & Agustinawati, 2019; Kraa, *et. al.*, 2018; Muhamad, 2015; Islam & Rahman, 2015; Kaura, 2013). Service features were important predictors of customer satisfaction in recent studies (Budiyono, *et. al.*, 2021; Khatab, Esmaeel, & Othman, 2019; Mohammad, 2015; Ateba, Maredza, Ohei, Deka, & Schutte, 2015; Ismail, Mubarack & Thulkifly, 2015). The research hypothesized that:

HO₁: Service features do not exert statistical influence on customer satisfaction in Southeast, Nigeria.

2.1.2 Service Process: A process is a method, mechanism, set of activities, and steps taken to exchange value with another party (ALafeef, 2020; Akbar & Basriani, 2020; Mahajan, 2017; Motwani & Shrimali, 2014; Al-Dmour, Al-Zu'bi, & Kakeesh, 2013). Commercial banks deploy services (Kumar, 2013; Chawla, 2013) and ensure that these services are strictly and systematically followed (Ekawati & Yasa, 2018). The banks make efforts to reduce the bulky accounts opening forms and save service time (Kraa, *et. al.*, 2018). The banking processes are made seamless, fast, and customer-friendly (ALafeef, 2020) to appeal to time-conscious customers (Kaura, 2013). Research has shown a statistical influence of the process on customer satisfaction (Budiyono, *et. al.*, 2021; Othman, Harun, Sadq, Rashid, Abdullah, Mohammed & Faeq, 2020; Khatab, Esmaeel, & Othman, 2019; Kraa, *et. al.*, 2018; Mohammad, 2015; Ateba, *et. al.*, 2015; Ismail, Mubarack & Thulkifly, 2015). This study hypothesized that:

HO₂: Service process has no statistical influence on customer satisfaction in Southeast, Nigeria.

2.1.3 Service Charge: The service charge is the price paid by bank customers. It is called fees, fares, tolls, rates, charges, and subscriptions by various service institutions (Palmer, 2008). Service charge is the value offered by customers to get a value in return (Akbar & Basriani, 2020; Braciníková & Matušínská, 2017; Al-Dmour, Al-Zu'bi, & Kakeesh, 2013). As a revenue generator and communication tool (ALafeef, 2020; Braciníková & Matušínská, 2017; Mahmood and Khan, 2014), service charge is used to penetrate new markets, maintain market share, defend a firm against competition, and achieve the firm's financial objectives (Palmer, 2008). The bank service charges include price lists, interest rates, discounts, allowances, margins, collateral, and payment options (Nouri & Soltani, 2015; Mahmood & Khan, 2014; Kumar, 2013; Kaura, 2013). Extant literature indicated a relationship between service charges and customer satisfaction (Budiyono, *et. al.*, 2021; Othman, Harun, Sadq, Rashid, Abdullah, Mohammed, & Faeq, 2020; Khatab, Esmaeel, & Othman, 2019; Ateba, *et. al.*, 2015; Ismail, Mubarack & Thulkifly, 2015). On the contrary, Mohammad (2015) found that service charges do not have a positive significant relationship with customer satisfaction in Northern, Nigeria. This survey hypothesized that:
HO₃: Service charges do not have a significant relationship with customer satisfaction in Southeast, Nigeria.

2.1.4 Service Communication: Service communication, promotion, or marketing communication is the process of establishing an understanding and cooperation of customers by providing useful banking information. It is the process of sending messages about the company's efforts and activities to various target groups (Basriani, 2020; Muhamad, 2015; Motwani & Shrimali, 2014; Kaura, 2013; Sreenivas, Srinivasarao & Rao, 2013). This service marketing strategy is used to attract customers and provide information about new services, interest rates, seasonal offers, and new branches (ALafeef, 2020; Mahmood & Khan, 2014). Service communication is the act of informing, educating, reminding, persuading, and engaging with customers before, during, and after service delivery. It is used to provide banking information; teach customer roles, refresh customer service knowledge, and convince customers to buy the bank's services. Service communication tools for banks include brochures, magazines, billboards, employee explanations, lucky draws, corporate programs, presentations, advertisements, digital marketing, and displays (ALafeef, 2020; Sintani, Mantikei, Anggariani & Agustinawati, 2019; Mahajan, 2017; Mahmood & Khan, 2014). Previous studies determined a statistical relationship between service communication and customer satisfaction (Budiyono, *et. al.*, 2021; Khatab, Esmaeel, & Othman, 2019; Ateba, *et. al.*, 2015; Ismail, Mubarack & Thulkifly, 2015), except in Northern, Nigeria (Mohammad, 2015). This survey hypothesized that:

HO₄: Service communication does not significantly relate to customer satisfaction in Southeast, Nigeria.

2.1.5 Service Encounter: Service encounter comprises service delivery points, delivery mode, and the service performer (Mahmood & Khan, 2014; Al-Dmour, Al-Zu'bi, & Kakeesh, 2013). It involves activities that facilitate service availability and accessibility (ALafeef, 2020; Olaleke, Borishade, Adeniyi, & Omolade, 2014, Motwani & Shrimali, 2014; Sreenivas, Srinivasarao & Rao, 2013). Service encounter includes bank branches and offices, service options, and automatic teller machines, ATMs (Sintani, *et. al.*, 2019). Shostack (1985) classified service encounters into physical, phone, and remote encounters. Physical service encounter involves customer-bank direct contact at offices, branches, and cash points (Nur & Istiqomah, 2015). A phone service encounter enables customers to conduct transactions over the phone while a remote service encounter uses self-service technology such as ATM, mobile, or internet banking facility to complete transactions. Service encounter was an important determinant of customer satisfaction (Budiyono, *et. al.*, 2021; Othman, *et. al.*, 2020; Khatab, Esmaeel, & Othman,

2019; Ismail, Mubarack & Thulkifly, 2015). Only one Northern Nigerian study established an insignificant influence of place on the satisfaction of customers (Mohammad, 2015). This research hypothesized that:

HO₅: Service encounters do not significantly relate to customer satisfaction in Southeast, Nigeria.

2.1.6 Service Participation: Service participation is the contribution of all human elements (service performers) in a face-to-face service encounter. The service performers are service employees, focal customers, other customers, and third-party service provider(s). These service participants contribute their time, effort, and other vital resources to the service encounter (Yim, Chan, & Lam, 2012). The interpersonal behavior of service performers and service discretion are key characteristics of service participants (Muhamad, 2015). Customers participate in bank service delivery by providing information, engaging in physical documentation, and making personal efforts for account opening, loan processing, or other services (Mahmood & Khan, 2014; Kaura, 2013). Customer participation is encouraged by employees' behaviors such as customers' courteous welcome, friendliness, understanding of customer problems, and empathy (Mahmood & Khan, 2014). It was shown that service participation positively relates to customer satisfaction (Budiyono, *et. al.*, 2021; Khatab, Esmaeel, & Othman, 2019; Kraa, *et al*, 2018, Ateba, *et. al.*, 2015; Ismail, Mubarack & Thulkifly, 2015) except in a Northern Nigerian survey (Mohammad, 2015). This research hypothesized that:

HO₆: Service participation does not positively relate to customer satisfaction in Southeast, Nigeria.

2.1.7 Service Evidence: Service evidence, physical evidence, service environment, physical infrastructure, or servicescape is a combination of tangible assets, touchpoints, and environment that facilitate service performance and communication (ALafeef, 2020; Kraa, *et. al.*, 2018; Muhamad, 2015; Islam & Rahman, 2015; Mahmood & Khan, 2014). Service evidence signifies the material evidence of service. This suggests the use of tangible resources to make up for the intangibility of service (Akbar & Basriani, 2020). The service evidence comprises bank logos, writing pads, annual reports, business cards, equipment, interiors, exteriors, parking facilities, color, passbooks, corporate brochures, financial reports, corporate statements, branded pens, and checkbooks (Akbar & Basriani, 2020; Islam & Rahman, 2015; Kumar, 2013). Service evidence is an important marketing cue that shapes customer perception, attitude, purchasing decisions, and service evaluation. It serves as a corporate image-building tool, differentiation technique, and service quality signal (Al Daebi & Al Waely, 2015; Kaura, 2013). Service evidence was an important predictor of customer satisfaction in previous studies (Budiyono, *et. al.*, 2021; Khatab, Esmaeel, & Othman, 2019; Kraa, *et. al.*, 2018; Mahajan, 2017; Mohammad, 2015; Ateba, *et. al.*, 2015; Ismail, Mubarack & Thulkifly, 2015). The research hypothesized that:

HO₇: Service evidence has no statistical relationship with customer satisfaction in Southeast, Nigeria.

2.2 Customer Satisfaction: Customer satisfaction is a feeling that service performance meets customer-perceived expectations (Zeithaml, Bitner & Gremler, 2009; Bracíníková & Matušínská, 2017; Kursunluoglu, 2011). Sintani, *et. al.* (2019) argued that satisfaction is measured by the customer's impression of services and that of bank facilities. Customer satisfaction is determined through service offerings and at the service point. Service processes and systems, voice tone, effective objection/complaint handling, employee dress, equipment, and physical setting tend to trigger customer satisfaction (Zeithaml, Bitner & Gremler, 2009).

Conceptual Framework

A service marketing strategy is a blend of service variables to meet customer requirements. Service features, service process, service charge, service communication, service encounter, service participation, and service evidence are strategically combined to achieve specific marketing objectives. The bank manager deploys the right

proportion of each or some of the SMSs to satisfy customers at a profit. Figure 2.6 shows that the service marketing variables are interdependent and they make individual contributions to achieve the expected outcome.

Figure 2.6: *Managing service marketing strategies to achieve customer satisfaction.*

Source: Survey 2023

3.0 Research Method

3.1 Sampling Procedure

This survey targeted twenty-five million, seven hundred and ninety-seven thousand, six hundred and twelve (25,797,612) adult bank customers in Southeast, Nigeria (CBN, 2019). The research used Yamane’s (1964) formula for a finite population to ascertain a sample size. The formula states that:

$$n = \frac{N}{[1 + N(e)^2]}$$

Where n = Sample size

N = The finite population

e = Level of significance (error margin)

1 = Unit (constant)

Therefore, the sample for the study was 400 adult bank customers. Thereafter, the study used Kumar's (1976) formula to allocate proportionate samples to the five states. The formula is stated as:

$$nh = \frac{n(Nh)}{N}$$

Where nh = The sample of each state.

n = The overall sample size.

Nh = Population of each state.

N = The overall population.

3.2 Measurement

The research scales were categorized into respondents' bio-data, SMSs, and customer satisfaction. Service features were measured using service brand name, financial service range, experience of staff, quickness of bank responses, and flexibility of service offerings (Thwala & Slabbert, 2018; Ahmad, Al-Qarni, Alsharqi, Qalai, & Kadi, 2013). Using Matzler, Wu"rtele, & Renzl's (2006) price service satisfaction scale, service charge was measured as price list, reasonability of price, predictability of changes in price, and conditions of service, explanation of price changes, and the tendency of having hidden cost. The measures of service communication consist of service information, service recommendations, service advertisement, and customer-customer interaction (Auh, Bell, McLeod, & Shih, 2007). Service encounter questions included bank branch location, payment over the counter, the functionality of banking equipment, electronic channels' ease of use, and telephone banking transactions (Shostack, 1985). The measures of service participants include employee professionalism, dedication, and empathy; customer contribution of time and effort, and fellow customers' compliance (Yim, Chan, & Lam, 2012; Auh, *et. al.*, 2007). Service evidence was measured as attractiveness of interior/exterior designs, employee appearance, parking space, fittings, and bank office layout (Karatepe, Yavas & Babakusc, 2005). The measures of the service process were ease of process, service usage time, complaint handling approach, use of electronic channels, and flexibility of service procedure. (Zeithaml, Bitner & Gremler, 2009; Sreenivas, Srinivasarao, & Rao, 2013). The customer satisfaction measurement includes response to unavailable/delayed service, response to admitted customer error, response to customer preferences, level of attention paid to customers, performance during emergencies, and response to potentially disruptive customers (Bitner, Booms, & Tetreault, 1990).

3.3 Analyses

The research used average variance extracted (AVE) to test the validity of the questionnaire. It was found that service features, service charge, service communication, service encounter, service participation, service process, service evidence, and customer satisfaction scored 0.515, 0.561, 0.573, 0.623, 0.544, 0.526, 0.557, and 0.585. The results met the benchmark of .50 for the convergent validity test (Wong, 2019). Furthermore, the scale reliability was tested with Cronbach Alpha to determine a proportionate variation of scale scores (Onodugo, Ugwuonah, & Ebinne, 2010). The reliability of the test instrument recorded 0.775, 0.804, 0.742, 0.868, 0.811, 0.767, 0.796, and 0.855 for service features, service charge, service communication, service encounter, service participation, service process, service evidence, as well as customer satisfaction. The research also met a minimum reliability coefficient of .70 (Pallant, 2007). After the preliminary analyses, standard multiple regression was used to analyze the research data.

4.0 Results

The survey used 322 (80.5%) valid responses for data analysis because they were considered sufficient enough.

Demographic Analysis

The research recorded the participation of 119 (37%) males and 203 (63%) females. Young adult participants (aged 20 – 40 years) outnumbered older ones (aged 41 - 60 years). 141 (43.8%) of the research participants were unmarried, 178 (55.3%) were married, 2 (0.6%) had divorced or were separated from their spouses, whereas 1 (0.3%) were widowed. The research established that low-income earners outnumbered those of high-income earners. The results revealed the eligibility of the respondents.

Standard Multiple Regression Result

Multiple regression assumptions were tested before the main analysis. The study met multicollinearity, normality, linearity, outlier, homoscedasticity, and independence of residuals assumptions. The survey met tolerance values and VIF standards given that the former recorded values that were less than .10 while the latter pulled scores that were not above .10 (Pallant, 2007).

Table 4: Standard Multiple Regression Result

Variable	Beta	t value	Sig.	Part	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)		4.149	.000			
Service features	.106	1.832	.068	.082	.597	1.675
Service process	.398	6.886	.000*	.308	.599	1.669
Service charge	.083	1.355	.176	.061	.540	1.853
Service communication	-.256	-4.882	.000*	-.219	.730	1.369
Service encounter	.024	.380	.704	.017	.497	2.014
Service Participation	.044	.758	.449	.034	.584	1.714
Service evidence	.067	1.201	.231	.054	.654	1.530
$R^2 = .370$; F value = 26.353						

Dependent variable: Customer Satisfaction

Source: Field Survey, 2023

The study determined a positive statistical effect of service process and service communication on the satisfaction of Southeast customers. Service process made a greater contribution to customer satisfaction than service communication. The result implied that an improvement in the standard of service process led to an increase in the level at which customers were satisfied. Also, an increase in the bank’s service communication efforts increased the satisfaction of Southeast customers. On the contrary, service features, service charges, service encounters, service participation, and service evidence had no statistical influence on customer satisfaction. Therefore, hypotheses 3 and 6 were rejected while hypotheses 1, 2, 4, 5, and 7 were not rejected. The model explained 37% of variance in the customer satisfaction.

5. Discussion

The research ascertained a statistical influence of the service process on the satisfaction of Southeast customers. This result was also reported in previous studies (Budiyono, *et. al.*, 2021; Othman, *et. al.*, 2020; Khatab, Esmaeel, & Othman, 2019; Kraa, *et. al.*, 2018; Ismail, Mubarack & Thulkify, 2015). This result suggested that a service flow was more important to customers than service features because bank customers needed instant service delivery. Southeast customers were more interested in bank services that help save some time than multiple

service options. The banks are advised to develop a customer-friendly service system that can reduce service time and increase service turnover. Another important predictor of customer satisfaction was service communication. This result was in line with previous research reports (Budiyono, *et. al.*, 2021; Khatab, Esmaeel, & Othman, 2019; Ateba, *et. al.*, 2015; Ismail, Mubarack & Thulkifly, 2015). The result suggested that effective service communication increased role clarity and customer commitment. The banks were advised to intensify efforts to provide timely financial information to facilitate customer commitment. The bank managers should use simple language to pass messages about service attributes and benefits to the target customers. The study also found insignificant statistical influence of service features, service charges, service encounters, service participation, and service evidence on customer satisfaction. In the same vein, there was an insignificant relationship between service charges, service encounters, service participation, and customer satisfaction in Northern Nigeria (Mohammad, 2015). The result implied that for every unit increase in service options; service channels; customer involvement; service facilities; and a reduction in service charge, there was little impact on the satisfaction of Southeast bank customers.

6. Direction for Further Studies

The research suggests a replication of the study in other service subsectors such as insurance, telecommunication, transportation, etc.

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Appendices

Appendix A

Section A: Demographic Characteristics

Instruction: Please tick your favorite option.

1. Gender (a) Male (b) Female
2. Age (a) 20 to 30 years (b) 31 to 40 years (c) 41 to 50 years (d) 51 to 60 years
(e) 61 years and above
3. Marital status (a) Single (b) Married (c) Divorced/Separated (d) Widowed
4. Monthly earning (a) Below N30,000 (b) N30,000 to N50,000 (c) N51,000 to N70,000 (d) N71,000 to N90,000 (e) N91,000 to N110,000 (f) N111,000 and above

Section B: Service Marketing Strategies

Instruction: Please show the extent of agreement to the statements in the table by circling numbers that represent Strongly Disagree (SD), Disagree (D), Neither Agree nor Disagree (N), Agree (A), or Strongly Agree (SA).

S/N	ITEM	SD	D	N	A	SA
12	International Journal of Interdisciplinary Research in Marketing and Management https://sadijournals.org/index.php/IJIRMM					

Service Features					
10	My bank has a unique brand name.	1	2	3	4 5
11	The bank offers many service options.	1	2	3	4 5
12	My bank has experienced staff.	1	2	3	4 5
13	I am confident that my bank responds quickly at all times.	1	2	3	4 5
14	The flexibility of my bank services to meet my expectations.	1	2	3	4 5
Service Charge					
15	The price list is clear and understandable	1	2	3	4 5
16	The bank charges are fair.	1	2	3	4 5
17	I expect changes in prices and conditions before they happen.	1	2	3	4 5
18	Changes in service charges are explained properly and timely.	1	2	3	4 5
19	All bank service charges are known to customers.	1	2	3	4 5
Service Communication					
20	I am aware of all the services provided by my bank.	1	2	3	4 5
21	I get service recommendations from my bank.	1	2	3	4 5
22	Service features/benefits are advertised.	1	2	3	4 5
23	Customers share service experiences.	1	2	3	4 5
Service Encounter					
24	My bank's branches/offices are close to my location.	1	2	3	4 5
25	Customers can withdraw money over the counter.	1	2	3	4 5
26	Banking equipment is always functional.	1	2	3	4 5
27	The bank's electronic channels are easy to use.	1	2	3	4 5
28	I conduct some bank transactions over the phone.	1	2	3	4 5
Service Participation					
29	The staff is professional, dedicated, nice, and empathetic.	1	2	3	4 5
30	I spend time to communicate my needs to the bank staff.	1	2	3	4 5
31	My suggestions are appreciated by the bank staff.	1	2	3	4 5
32	I play my role in the bank service delivery.	1	2	3	4 5
33	Fellow customers comply with bank instructions.	1	2	3	4 5
Service Process					
34	Account opening is very easy.	1	2	3	4 5
35	Loan processing takes a short period.	1	2	3	4 5
36	Complaints are handled instantly.	1	2	3	4 5
37	Employee services are supported with digital services.	1	2	3	4 5
38	The bank staff uses flexible service procedures.	1	2	3	4 5
Service Evidence					
39	The bank's interior/exterior designs are visually attractive.	1	2	3	4 5
40	I like the appearance of my bank staff.	1	2	3	4 5
41	My bank has adequate, secured space for parking vehicles.	1	2	3	4 5
42	I like the fittings in my bank.	1	2	3	4 5
43	The office layout of my bank is attractive.	1	2	3	4 5

Section C: Customer Satisfaction

Instruction: In each service situation, please circle the number that best expresses how satisfied or dissatisfied you felt with your bank service experience.

S/N	Items	Very Dissatisfied	Somewhat Dissatisfied	Neither nor Satisfied	Somewhat Satisfied	Very Satisfied
64	Response to unavailable/delayed service.	1	2	3	4	5
65	Response to admitted customer error.	1	2	3	4	5
66	Response to customer requirements.	1	2	3	4	5
67	Level of attention paid to customers	1	2	3	4	5
68	Performance during emergencies.	1	2	3	4	5
69	Response to potentially disruptive customers.	1	2	3	4	5

Thank you.

Appendix B

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.608 ^a	.370	.356	4.14069

a. Predictors: (Constant), Service Evidence, Service Encounter, Service Charge, Service Communication, Service Process, Service Features, Service Participation

b. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

ANOVA^a

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	3162.794	7	451.828	26.353	.000 ^b
	Residual	5383.629	314	17.145		
	Total	8546.422	321			

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction

b. Predictors: (Constant), Service Evidence, Service Encounter, Service Charge, Service Communication, Service Process, Service Features, Service Participation
Coefficients^a

Model	Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.	95.0% Confidence Interval for B		Correlations			Collinearity Statistics	
	B	Std. Error	Beta			Lower Bound	Upper Bound	Zero-order	Partial	Partial	Tolerance	VIF
(Constant)	7.247	1.746		4.149	.000	3.811	10.683					
Service Features	.136	.074	.106	1.832	.068	-.010	.282	.355	.103	.082	.597	1.675
Service Process	.497	.072	.398	6.886	.000	.355	.640	.519	.362	.308	.599	1.669
Service Charge	.092	.068	.083	1.355	.176	-.041	.225	.434	.076	.061	.540	1.853
Service Communication	-.285	.058	-.256	-4.882	.000	-.399	-.170	-.256	-.266	-.219	.730	1.369
Service Encounter	.028	.072	.024	.380	.704	-.115	.170	-.059	.021	.017	.497	2.014
Service Participation	.061	.080	.044	.758	.449	-.097	.218	.034	.043	.034	.584	1.714
Service Evidence	.087	.072	.067	1.201	.231	-.055	.229	.360	.068	.054	.654	1.530

a. Dependent Variable: Customer Satisfaction